

Appendix for

**Ensuring Epidemiological Consistency in Risk-Stratified Health Economic Models: A Case Study
in Breast Cancer Screening**

Supplement 1: Scoping Review Materials

The scoping review discussed in the manuscript was performed to underline the gap of our novel approach and to assess whether our approach is, in fact, novel. We employed a broad search string ((cancer AND screening) AND (" Markov model" OR " Markov models" OR " Markov chain") AND (" Risk Stratification" OR " risk stratified" OR " Risk-based") aimed to mimic the search strategy a health economic researcher might employ to start a risk-stratified cancer screening evaluation. We included Markov models aimed at risk-stratified cancer screening, excluding those that worked on pre-stratified populations (meaning that the model made no stratification itself but only modelled a single high-risk population).

Besides ascertaining the relevant gap for our proposed method, we looked at three specific characteristics in the articles. Namely the source of the (1) initial transition probabilities (*TP*) (before any risk-adjustments), (2) the method of applying risk-stratification (*RS*) in the model, and (3) whether the epidemiological predictions were explicitly verified in the paper. For the first question, we have three general categories for the *TP* sources: *internal literature* (dedicated observational studies, pilot studies, or epidemiological studies directly focused on the same population as the model), *public registry data* (raw prevalence and/or incidence data from which transition probabilities are extracted) and *external literature* (studies that published a model about a different target population). In some cases the article discusses taking the model from an external source without explicitly mentioning the *TP* one way or the other, in which case we assume that the external model is also the *TP* source. We assumed that generally, internal literature is a better source than national registry data, which itself is better than using an external source. For the second question, we found that all models (100%) directly embedded the risk-adjustment directly into the *TP*, validating our assessment that our approach was a novel approach. We further looked at the most used methods of applying the risk-adjustments (using a multiplier method such as a risk-ratio, using pre-adjusted probabilities from the external source, or making an internal estimation of the adjusted *TP*). Lastly, we checked if the article explicitly validates the epidemiological results, differentiating between studies that mentioned doing this and studies that explicitly showed the results. While showing these results is important for a number of reasons (it increases transparency, trust, and helps other researchers select the best performing models) we also point out that not showing these results is not always the choice of the researcher.

Flow diagram of review with summary results of included articles.

Result tables of included articles.

Ref	DOI	Country	Cancer	Model Type	Primary TP Source	Epidemiological Validation
1A	10.1371/journal.pone.0202796	UK	Bladder	Decision Tree & Markov	External Literature	Yes, Discussed
2A	10.1093/jnci/djae019	USA	Breast	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
3A	10.1186/s12913-021-06396-2	Singapore	Breast	Markov Cohort Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	No
4A	10.1038/s41598-023-29985-z	China	Breast	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	Yes, Shown
5A	10.1371/journal.pone.0217213	Germany	Breast	Markov MicroSim Model	National Registry Data	No
6A	10.1016/j.jval.2017.12.022	Germany	Breast	Markov MicroSim Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	Yes, Shown
7A	10.1186/s12913-024-11226-2	Malawi	Cervical	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
8A	10.1111/jgh.15033	Japan	Colorectal	Markov Cohort Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	Yes, Discussed
9A	10.1186/1471-2407-14-261	Australia	Colorectal	Markov MicroSim Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	Yes, Discussed
10A	10.1007/s10198-017-0901-y	Japan	Gastric	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
11A	10.1136/gutjnl-2021-325948	China	Gastric	Markov Cohort Model	National Registry Data	Yes, Shown
12A	10.1016/j.jval.2021.04.1286	Australia	Liver	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
13A	10.1038/ctg.2017.26	USA	Liver	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	Yes, Shown
14A	10.1186/s12916-024-03292-4	China	Lung	Markov Cohort Model	National Registry Data	Yes, Shown
15A	10.3389/fpubh.2024.1375533	China	Nasal	Markov Cohort Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	Yes, Discussed
16A	10.1016/j.ctarc.2024.100791	Iran	Prostate	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
17A	10.3390/genes10090641	Taiwan	Prostate	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	No
18A	10.1371/journal.pmed.1002998	USA	Prostate	Markov Cohort Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	No
19A	10.1002/pros.22964	Finland	Prostate	Markov Cohort Model	Internal Literature / Pilot study	Yes, Discussed
20A	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.37657	UK	Prostate	Markov MicroSim Model	External Literature	No
21A	10.1016/j.gie.2021.08.008	China	Stomach	Markov Cohort Model	External Literature	Yes, Discussed
22A	10.1007/s40273-022-01160-8	China	Stomach	Markov MicroSim Model	External Literature	Yes, Discussed
23A	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.37657	USA	Prostate	Markov Cohort Model	National Registry Data	Yes, Shown

Table 1: General characteristics of Included articles, source of the primary Transition Probabilities (TP) and if the article discussed the epidemiological validation.

Ref	DOI	Risk Stratification in Model	Risk Stratification Method	Embedding Method
1A	10.1371/journal.pone.0202796	Yes, Risk factors	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
2A	10.1093/jnci/djae019	Yes, Risk factors	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
3A	10.1186/s12913-021-06396-2	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
4A	10.1038/s41598-023-29985-z	Yes, Risk factors (history, breast tissue)	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
5A	10.1371/journal.pone.0217213	Yes, Lifetime Risk	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
6A	10.1016/j.jval.2017.12.022	Yes, Risk factors (history, breast tissue)	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
7A	10.1186/s12913-024-11226-2	Yes, Risk factors (history, HIV)	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
8A	10.1111/jgh.15033	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
9A	10.1186/1471-2407-14-261	Yes, History	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
10A	10.1007/s10198-017-0901-y	Yes, Risk factors	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
11A	10.1136/gutjnl-2021-325948	Yes, Risk factors (history, Smoking)	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
12A	10.1016/j.jval.2021.04.1286	Yes, History	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
13A	10.1038/ctg.2017.26	Yes, Risk factors	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
14A	10.1186/s12916-024-03292-4	Yes, Risk factors (history, smoking tissue)	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
15A	10.3389/fpubh.2024.1375533	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
16A	10.1016/j.ctarc.2024.100791	Yes, PSA	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
17A	10.3390/genes10090641	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
18A	10.1371/journal.pmed.1002998	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
19A	10.1002/pros.22964	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Direct Estimation of TP
20A	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.37657	Yes, History	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
21A	10.1016/j.gie.2021.08.008	Yes, Lifetime Risk	Embedded into TP	Embedded in External Sources
22A	10.1007/s40273-022-01160-8	Yes, History	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios
23A	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.37657	Yes, PRS stratified	Embedded into TP	Risk Ratios

Table 2: Risk-stratification in included articles, including the basis for the risk-stratification (general risk factors, Polygenic Risk Scores, family history, medical or social factors), the overall method of including a risk-adjustment to the model (in all cases it was directly embedded into the transition probabilities) and if embedded, in what way.

References of Included articles

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Supplement 2: Numerical Example calculation of method

Age group and size		Incidence by stage, cases WA p.y.		Incidence Rate		Conditional Survival Probability		Cumulative Cancer-free Survival	
		St. 0	St. 1-4	St. 0	St. 1-4	St. 0	St. 1-4	St. 0	St. 1-4
j	N _j	C _{0j}	C _{1-4j}	I _{0j}	I _{1-4j}	q _{0j}	q _{1-4j}	S _{0j}	S _{1-4j}
0 - 9	340,191	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	98.10%	86.26%
Oct/19	372,442	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	98.10%	86.26%
20 - 29	382,265	1.9	22.6	0.00%	0.01%	100.00%	99.94%	98.10%	86.26%
30 - 39	429,841	28.5	203.9	0.01%	0.05%	99.93%	99.53%	98.10%	86.31%
40 - 49	429,095	130.5	796.3	0.03%	0.19%	99.70%	98.16%	98.17%	86.72%
50 - 59	461,210	246.4	1342.6	0.05%	0.29%	99.47%	97.13%	98.47%	88.35%
60 - 69	430,583	247.9	1553.3	0.06%	0.36%	99.43%	96.45%	98.99%	90.96%
70 - 79	325,830	101	1186.6	0.03%	0.36%	99.69%	96.42%	99.56%	94.31%
80-85	109,433	27.7	483.4	0.03%	0.44%	99.87%	97.81%	99.87%	97.81%

Tot. 3,280,890	783.8	5588.8	$I_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{N_j}$	$q_{ij} = (1 - I_{ij})^{10}$	$S_{ij} = \prod_{k=j}^j q_{ij}$
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Table 3: Example calculation of the pre-stratification at-risk groups, using national incidence data. The first step involves calculating the incidence rate, then the conditional cancer free survival probability, which leads to the cumulative cancer-free survival. Taking the remainder of these cumulative cancer-free survival rates gives the at-risk proportion of the specific age-group. The relevant formula for the calculation is shown in the bottom row.

Age group and size		Incidence by stage, p.y.		Distribution of Incidence		Conditional Survival Adjustment		Conditional Transition Rate	
		St. 0	St. 1	St. 0	St. 1	St. 0	St. 1	St. 0	St. 1
j	N _j	C _i	C _j	π _{0j}	π _{1j}	P _{0j}	P _{1j}	λ _{0j}	λ _{1j}
0 - 9	340,191	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Oct/19	372,442	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
20 - 29	382,265	1.9	11.6	0.24%	0.42%	100.00%	100.00%	0.24%	0.42%
30 - 39	429,841	28.5	91.5	3.63%	3.34%	99.76%	99.58%	3.64%	3.35%
40 - 49	429,095	130.5	373.6	16.65%	13.63%	96.12%	96.24%	17.32%	14.17%
50 - 59	461,210	246.4	735.2	31.44%	26.83%	79.48%	82.61%	39.56%	32.48%
60 - 69	430,583	247.9	883.1	31.62%	32.23%	48.04%	55.77%	65.83%	57.79%
70 - 79	325,830	101	500.7	12.89%	18.27%	16.42%	23.54%	78.50%	77.61%
80-85	109,433	27.7	144.5	3.53%	5.27%	3.53%	5.27%	100.00%	100.00%

Tot. 3,280,890	783.8	2740.1	$\pi_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sum C_i}$	$P_{ij} = 1 - \sum_{k=j-1}^j \pi_k$	$\lambda_{ij} = \frac{\pi_{ij}}{P_{ij}}$
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Table 4: Example calculation of the conditional transition probability of the first transition from at-risk to cancer. The first step involves calculating the age-distribution of the incidence. Then the conditional cancer-free survival adjustment is calculated. This can be thought of as the proportion of the at-risk group that has yet to develop cancer. The conditional rate is then calculated as the division of the age-distribution by the survival adjustment. In simple terms, the portion of the at-risk group that is pre-predicted to get cancer at that specific age.

Supplement 3: Markov Model Diagram

Figure 1: Markov Model diagram of the complete model with 4 distinct risk-groups. Each group has a separate proportion of at-risk individuals (higher proportions in the elevated and high risk-groups) and individual levels of screening rates based on age and group.